

ISSN-0970-7603
Peer Reviewed Journal

भारतीय शिक्षा शोध पत्रिका

BHARATIYA EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH JOURNAL

वर्ष 34, अंक 1, जनवरी-जून 2015
Vol. 34, No.1, January-June-2015

भारतीय शिक्षा शोध संस्थान

सरस्वती कुंज, निराला नगर, लखनऊ-226020 (उत्तर प्रदेश)

Research Institute of Bharatiya Education

Saraswati Kunj, Nirala Nagar, Lucknow-226020 (Uttar Pradesh)

विषय-सूची

Contents

* सम्पादकीय / Editorial		(iii)
शोधपत्र / Research Articles		
* A Study of Attitude of High School teachers about the Information Communication Technology (ICT)	Dr. Lal Singh	1
* समावेष्टित शिक्षा विद्यालयों में विशेष आवश्यकता वाले विद्यार्थियों को प्रदत्त सुविधाओं का अध्ययन	डॉ० देवेन्द्र आमेटा राकेश कुमार तिनका	7
* Environmental Education curriculam in Teacher Training Programmes : An Analytical Study	Kaushal Kedawat	12
* Quality of Teacher Education : What and How	Neetu Yadav	22
* To study the participation of the students in annual sports of the College	Dr. S.C. Bahuguna	27
* A study of Environmental literacy among Masses : In Relation to their Sex, Locality and Level of Education	Dr. Sunita Sundriyal Pro. B.R. Kukreti	31
* पूछताछ प्रशिक्षण प्रतिमान एवं पारम्परिक विधि का तुलनात्मक (प्रायोगिक) अध्ययन	डॉ. रमा शर्मा डॉ. बलिदान जैन	42
* A Comparative Study of Organisational Climate of Residential & Non Residential Schools	Rishi Goel Dr. Madhu Gupta	45
* The effect of Power Point Presentations on Achievement Motivation of B.Ed. Teacher Trainees	Dr. Pratibha Sagar Prof. N.N. Pandey	51
* क्यों क्या एवं कैसे किया जाये सतत् एवं व्यापक मूल्यांकन	शिवांगी सिंह	57
शोध टिप्पणी / Research Notes		
* Need for Environment Friendly Child Education	Dr. Roli Rai	61
* टैगोर के शिक्षा दर्शन में निहित आध्यात्मिक मानवतावाद	डॉ. रश्मि श्रीवास्तव	64
* राष्ट्रीय शिक्षा के सन्दर्भ में विचार : संकल्पना एवं स्वरूप	डॉ० शिवभूषण त्रिपाठी	67
विविध / Miscellaneous		
* शोधपत्र प्रारूप		69
* Formate of Letter		70
* ग्रन्थ समीक्षा : किशोर एवं युवाओं की मनोवृत्तियों का विकास	डॉ० आई०पी० शर्मा	71
* सामयिक गतिविधियाँ		72

The Effect of PowerPoint presentations on Achievement Motivation of B.Ed. Teacher Trainees

Dr. Pratibha Sagar *

Prof. N.N. Pandey**

सारांश

वर्तमान अध्ययन में भावी अध्यापकों की उपलब्धि अभिप्रेरणा पर पावर प्वाइंट प्रस्तुतीकरण के प्रभाव को देखा गया है। यह महात्मा ज्योतिबा फुले रुहेलखण्ड विश्वविद्यालय, बरेली के वी0एड0 (विशेषज्ञता) के दो कक्षाओं (प्रत्येक में 62 विद्यार्थी) पर किया गया है, जिसमें एक को व्याख्यान के साथ पावर प्वाइंट से तथा दूसरे को परम्परागत व्याख्यान विधि से पढ़ाया गया। दोनों कक्षाओं को एक ही विषय वस्तु समान समय तक पढ़ाई गई। पढ़ाने का कार्य 34 कार्य दिवसों तक चला। पढ़ाने के पूर्व एवं बाद में विद्यार्थियों पर उपलब्धि अभिप्रेरणा परीक्षण प्रशासित किया गया। प्राप्त प्रदत्तों के विश्लेषण हेतु प्रसरण सह विश्लेषण का प्रयोग किया गया। विश्लेषणोपरांत पाया गया कि प्रायोगिक एवं नियंत्रित समूह की उपलब्धि अभिप्रेरणा में सार्थक अंतर नहीं है। लड़कों एवं लड़कियों की उपलब्धि अभिप्रेरणा में सार्थक अंतर पाया गया। पाठ्यवस्तु प्रस्तुतीकरण की विधि एवं लिंग की अन्तःक्रिया का सार्थक प्रभाव नहीं पाया गया।

Computer technology has become an integral part of instruction at the university education procedures. Some instructors have enthusiastically adopted technological innovations in their classrooms (Craig and Amernic, 2006), while others have resisted the trend (Stewart, 2001). So, the debate on the importance of using computer technology in developing the educational process remains as uncertain as it is unsettling (Watson et al., 2007) which attracts more attention as such technology provides several advantages on traditional education and has the potential to enhance teaching and learning (Amare, 2006). One form of this technology is software that generates slides for presenting course material. While there are several presentation packages in the markets, PowerPoint became most common (Daniels et al., 2007). The PowerPoint presentation software is particularly attractive as it is user friendly, easy to learn, requires limited planning, is very versatile, and, provided the appropriate software and hardware is available, enables supporting materials such as slides and handouts for lectures to be prepared relatively quickly and inexpensively (Grandgenett et al., 1995). PowerPoint allows a lecturer to take advantage of the educational benefits of using visual aids and technology in lectures in order to improve the effectiveness of teaching and learning. Teaching with PowerPoint does not necessarily involve radical changes to teaching approaches.

Arousal is one of the key constructs in the study of human emotion and motivation. In fact, the presentations containing high levels of sensory stimulation are generally associated with high levels of audience arousal (Grabe, 2000). One could conclude that PowerPoint presentations, which stimulate the visual and auditory senses, should augment students' arousal levels. In a competitive society or set up, the desire to excel over others or to achieve a higher level than one's peers is more intensified which in turn may lead to a stronger drive

* Assistant Professor, Department of Education, MJP Rohilkhand University, Bareilly.

** Professor, Department of Education, MJP Rohilkhand University, Bareilly.

or motive to achieve something or everything that is essential to beat others in the race and consequently experience a sense of pride and pleasure in the achievement.

Need for Achievement (nAch) (McClelland, 1961; McClelland & Winter, 1969) is one of the psychological motives that play an important role in success and achievements of a man. Motivation as an academic engagement refers to "cognitive, emotional, and behavioural indicators of student investment in and attachment to education" (Tucker, Zayco & Herman, 2002). People with high achievement motives will act in ways that will help them to outperform others, meet or surpass some standard of excellence, or do something unique (Schmidt & Frieze, 1997). All students are influenced by a need to achieve to a certain degree. Those students, who hold a high desire of success, work hard to achieve (Zenzen, 2002). According to Maehr (2008) achievement motivation is largely social-psychological in nature. It often occurs within groups, where interpersonal interactions can undermine or facilitate engagement in the tasks to be done. In general achievement motivation is expectancy at finding satisfaction in mastery of difficult and challenging performances whereas in the field of education it particularly stands for the pursuit of excellence. From teacher's point of view, achievement motivation can be taken as active interest of pupils in the areas of learning. One of the major problems of teachers is to make his pupils achievement oriented, so that they can make effective use of their intellectual aspect for achieving the academic progress for which they are potentially capable. Because presentation technology can be used as a teaching tool, it would be beneficial to determine if it has any effect on achievement motivation in students. Technology should not be used just for technology sake; it should have a purpose related to achievement and motivation of the learner. No studies have been found to know the effect of PowerPoint presentation on achievement motivation of B.Ed. teacher trainees.

In the present investigation achievement-motivation is student's willingness, need, desire and compulsion to participate in, and be successful in, the learning process through PowerPoint presentations which will be measured through standardised test.

Objectives

In view of the above-mentioned considerations, the present investigation aims at following objectives:

1. To study the effect of PowerPoint presentation on achievement motivation of B.Ed. teacher trainees.
2. To find out gender differences in achievement motivation of B.Ed. teacher trainees.
3. To find out the effect of interaction between gender and teaching method on academic motivation of B.Ed. teacher trainees.

Hypotheses

Keeping in view the objectives of the study, the following hypotheses are formulated in null form:

H₀₁: There is no significance difference in the mean achievement motivation of B.Ed. teacher trainees taught by lecture method and lecture accompanied by PowerPoint presentation.

H₀₂: Boys and girls do not differ significantly in relation to their academic motivation.

H₀₃: Teaching method by gender of B.Ed. teacher trainees will not significantly affect academic motivation.

Methodology

This research was experimental in nature where pre-test –post-test, non equivalent control group design was used. Three B.Ed. specialization courses run in MJP Rohilkhand University, Bareilly campus, out of which teacher trainees of B.Ed. (Specialization in Vocational Education) and B.Ed. (Specialization in Educational Computing) groups were chosen. Two groups B.Ed. (Educational Computing), the experimental group, taught through PowerPoint presentations and B.Ed. Vocational Education, the control group, taught through traditional lecture method, were selected for the study. One intact class served as the experimental group and the other as the control group. Treatments were assigned randomly.

In the present study, for the purpose of measuring achievement motivation, Achievement Motive Test, ACMT – by V.P. Bhargava has been used. Teacher competence was controlled as the researcher herself taught both the experimental and control groups. Length of instruction was also controlled as each teaching session in each group lasted for one period of 40 minutes. Teaching session was planned for morning and afternoon time for control group and experimental group respectively on one day and next day morning time was allotted to

experimental group and afternoon time for control group. Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to analyse data where pre-test achievement motivation scores was taken as covariate. The total experimentation procedure was planned and organized in successive steps in order to facilitate proper collection of data. Firstly achievement motivation test was administered for pre-test scores then both the groups were taught for 34 working days. After a gap of two days, achievement motivation test was again administered for post-test scores.

Analysis and Discussion

2X2 analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was carried out on the data yielded through achievement motivation tests. Table 1.1 presents means and standard deviations for the various groups and the results of ANCOVA for achievement motivation for AT-post have been shown in Table 1.2.

Table 1.1 ACMT – Means and standard deviation

Table 1.2 Summary of ANCOVA for ACMT

A perusal of the above table reveals that the F value for the main effect of teaching method on achievement motivation was not significant ($F=0.011, p>0.05$). The non significant F tells that the experimental and control groups do not differ in achievement motivation. Hence, the hypothesis that “There is no significant difference in the mean achievement motivation of B.Ed. teacher trainees taught by lecture method and lecture accompanied by PowerPoint presentation” is accepted. The main effect for gender was found to be significant ($F = 7.213, p < 0.01$). The significant F – Value means that boys and girls differ in their achievement motivation. Hence the hypothesis that – “Boys and girls do not differ significantly in relation to their academic motivation” is rejected. The interaction between group and gender was found to be non significant ($F = 0.475, p > 0.05$). It means that boys and girls do not differ significantly in achievement motivation under the two teaching methods, PowerPoint and traditional method. Therefore, the hypothesis that “Teaching method by gender of B.Ed. teacher trainees will not significantly affect academic motivation” was accepted.

To further probe into the matter, adjusted means for ACMT post were calculated. These means have been shown in Table 1.3.

Table 1.3 Adjusted Means – Achievement Motivation

A look at the above table reveals that the mean of experimental group (23.958), taught through lecture with PowerPoint presentations is almost similar to that of control group (23.876). Thus the group taught through PowerPoint and the group taught through traditional method of teaching have equal effect on achievement motivation. The adjusted means for Achievement Motivation post-test for different groups reveals that boys (mean = 24.936) achieved higher than girls (mean = 22.897).

To further explain the effect of interaction, graphs were plotted between the adjusted means for ACMT-post means (Table 1.3), and the same has been presented in figure 1.

Figure 1. Adjusted Means – Achievement Motivation

This means that lecture supported by PowerPoint does not produce higher achievement motivation. The factors responsible for this difference may be including the Indian patriarchal society in which boys are considered to be the bread earner of the family. The responsibility of being the central point of family, boys seem to be more motivated as compared to girls. Moreover, generally boys come from lower socio economic status. Having a glance at socio-economic background of the B.Ed. teacher trainees, it was found that majority of boys were from lower to middle income group and majority of girls had good socio-economic status. So, girls were quite familiar with electronic gadgets like mobile, computer and internet etc. So may be boys were motivated because they found technology attractive and interesting. No study could be located in congruence with or contradicting this finding as well. However, it was concluded that boys and girls benefit equally in achievement motivation under the two teaching methods, PowerPoint and traditional method.

Implications

It is important for both parents, and educators, to understand why promoting and encouraging academic motivation from an early age is imperative. Achievement motivation is one of the crucial psychological factors determining future academic and occupational success at any age. Because students form self-concepts, values, and beliefs

about their abilities at a young age, the development of early academic motivation has significant implications for later academic careers. A great deal of research has found that students high in academic motivation are more likely to have increased levels of academic achievement and have lower dropout rates (Blank, 1997). Therefore, general and professional education should be completed with trainings focused on psychological skills useful and desirable in everyday life.

The traditional lecture has been criticised as encouraging surface rather than deep learning as it may not necessarily stimulate thinking. The simple transmission of information through a lecture is not an effective approach for meeting the goals of helping students become independent, critical problem solvers, able to interact with their peers in social and employment situations. Aside from threats of obsolescence, pedagogically lecturing is a flawed approach to teaching and must be replaced by more effective teaching paradigms. So the traditional lectures are replaced with information delivered by computers in the form of PowerPoint presentations as these presentations are more eye-catching and interesting, attention capturing which promotes higher order thinking for a student in the classroom setting.

All innovations require more time, money, energy, and patience in their implementation. Initially one may face certain challenges in using PowerPoint in classrooms but the gains promised are worth a trial. Use of computers in teaching learning environment in teacher education is viewed as one of the most challenging aspect in majority of Indian teacher education institutions. One of the contributing factors to this apprehension is the method our teachers use in classrooms. An urgent need is there to provide instructional strategies that can be used to integrate ICT in classrooms of prospective teachers. The present research shows that lecture supported with PowerPoint presentations can be one such strategy.

One of the key principles of effective teaching is that speech complimented by appropriate visual supporting aids is more likely to be remembered. Students will therefore follow a lecture more easily if they are using more than one of their senses. Visual cues can clarify a statement, eliminate ambiguity, add detail and are therefore powerful instructional aid. Visual aids like PowerPoint presentations improve communication in lectures because they procure attention, add variety, save time when explaining complicated points, introduce, summarise or integrate ideas, illustrate things which can only be explained graphically. By using such type of learning material, teachers can improve the understanding and knowledge and motivate the learners in any subjects. Even, in absence of teachers, it can engage students and prevent wastage of their time. Moreover, for effective learning, method of teaching and structure of content should be matched with intellectual development of learner. Keeping in view the above conclusion, it is suggested that in teacher training institutions, there should be modernization of lectures with proper integration of technology to improve classroom teaching.

Consulted Literature:

- Amare, N. (2006). **To slideware or not to slideware: students' experiences with PowerPoint vs. lecture.** *Journal of Technical Writing and Communication*, 36, 297-308.
- Blank, W. (1997). **Authentic instruction.** In W.E. Blank & S. Harwell (Eds.), *Promising practices for connecting high school to the real world* (pp. 15-21). Tampa, FL: University of South Florida. (ERIC Document Reproduction Service No. ED 407 586)
- Craig, R.J. & Amernic, J.H. (2006). **PowerPoint presentation technology and the dynamics of teaching.** *Innovative Higher Education*, 31, 147-160.
- Daniels, L., J. Kane, & B. Rosario (2007). **The impact of PowerPoint on student performance, course evaluations, and preferences in economics courses: Experiment at three institution,** paper presented at the annual meetings of the allied social science association, Chicago.
- Grabe, M. E. (2000). **Packaging television news: The effects of tabloid on information processing and evaluative responses.** *Journal of Broadcasting and Electronic Media*, 44, 581- 598.
- Grandgenett, D., Grandgenett, N., Topp, N. & Benton, J. (1995). **Using computer Assisted Presentations: Suggestions from the Audience.** *Educational Technology Review*, 19-22.

- Maehr, M. L. (2008). **Culture and achievement motivation**, *International Journal of Psychology*, 43: 5, 917-918.
- McClelland, D.C. (1961). *The achieving society*. Princeton, New Jersey: Van Nostrand.
- McClelland, D.C. & Winter, D.G. (1969). *Motivating economic achievement*. New York: Free Press.
- Schmidt L. C. & I. H. Frieze (1997): **A mediational model of power, affiliation and achievement motives and power involvement**. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 4, 425-446.
- Stewart, T. A. (2001). **Ban it now! Friends don't let friends use PowerPoint**, *Fortune*, 143, 210.
- Tucker, C. M., Zayco, R. A., & Herman, K. C. (2002). **Teacher and child variables as predictors of academic engagement among low-income African American children**. *Psychology in the Schools*, 39(4), 477-488.
- Watson, S. F., Apostolou, B., Hassell, J. M., and Webber, S. A. (2007). **Accounting education literature review (2003-2005)**, *Journal of Accounting Education*, 25, 1-58.
- Zenzen, T.G. (2002). *Achievement Motivation*, Dissertation, Retrieved from <http://www2.uwstout.edu/content/lib/thesis/2002/2002zenzent.pdf>

Table 1.1 ACMT – Means and standard deviation

		N	Mean	Standard Devision
ACMT Pre	Control Boys	49	16.39	4.76
	Control Girls	13	14.92	3.50
	Total	62	16.08	4.54
	Exp. Boys	40	18.90	5.70
	Exp. Girls	22	19.14	4.56
	Total	62	18.98	5.28
ACMT Post	Control Boys	49	24.14	4.21
	Control Girls	13	22.00	3.74
	Total	62	23.69	4.18
	Exp. Boys	40	25.83	4.20
	Exp. Girls	22	23.36	4.69
	Total	62	24.95	4.50

Table 1.2 Summary of ANCOVA for ACMT

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	F
Group (Teaching method)	0.147	1	0.147	0.011
Gender	98.808	1	98.808	7.213**
Teaching method x Gender	6.500	1	6.500	0.475
Error	1630.048	119	13.698	
Total	75708.00	124		

** - Significant at 0.01 level of significance

Table 1.3 Adjusted Means Achievement – Motivation

ACMT	Control	Experimental	Total
Boys	24.633	25.239	24.936
Girls	23.118	22.676	22.897
Total	23.876	23.958	23.917

Figure 1. Adjusted Means – Achievement Motivation

सद्व्यवहार

दिनचर्या

संस्कार

निर्माण

स्वास्थ्य रक्षा

सत्यनिष्ठा

संयम-ब्रह्मचर्य

व्यवस्थाप्रियता

धर्म-निष्ठा

स्वावलम्बन

शिष्टाचार

साहस (वीरव्रत)

स्वच्छता

संकल्प शक्ति

दायित्व बोध
परिवार, समाज,
सृष्टि के प्रति

अनुशासन

सत्यनिष्ठा

धैर्य

आत्मविश्वास

प्रेम
(अहिंसा)

संयम-ब्रह्मचर्य

कृतज्ञता

सृजनशीलता

वैज्ञानिक दृष्टिकोण

अस्तेय

